

Secrets for Success in Business

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Abstract

Business has become an essential part of the modern world. It is an economic activity, which is related to continuous and regular production and distribution of goods and services for satisfying human wants. It can be privately owned or state-owned. Every business requires some form of investments and adequate customers to whom the output can be sold to make the profit.

A successful entrepreneur has to possess three basic qualities. First, they need to learn more things. Second, they should try more things. Third, they have to persist longer than anyone else.

To realize the full potential and to achieve the business goals probable entrepreneurs must develop the virtues of integrity, courage and persistence. They have to practice the qualities of clarity, competence, creativity, concentration and continuous action as natural as breathing. They have to accept the complete responsibility for their life and everything that happens to them, and especially for the way they think in every area.

The secret of a successful business is that, if you learn more things, try more things and persist longer, you will succeed greatly. If you launch toward your goal and resolve in advance to never give up, your success is virtually guaranteed.

Keywords: Business, entrepreneur.

Introduction

Business has become an essential part of the modern world. It is an economic activity, which is related to continuous and regular production and distribution of goods and services for satisfying human wants. It can be privately owned or state-owned. Every business requires some form of investments and adequate customers to whom the output can be sold to make the profit.

Stephenson defines business as, "The regular production or purchase and sale of goods undertaken with an objective of earning the profit and acquiring wealth through the satisfaction of human wants."

According to Dicksee, "Business refers to a form of activity conducted with an objective of earning profits for the benefit of those on whose behalf the activity is conducted."

Lewis Henry defines business as, "Human activity directed towards producing or acquiring wealth through buying and selling of goods."

The term business means continuous production and distribution of goods and services with the aim of earning profits under uncertain market conditions.

Review of Literature

J.S. Saini and B.S. Rathore (2001) in their book titled Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice, deal with entrepreneurial philosophy, where the success of entrepreneurs has been discussed. According to the authors, the success of an entrepreneur depends on the entrepreneur's willingness to hold responsibility for his work.

Dr. A. Peter (2004) in his book Youth Entrepreneurship Everywhere explains youth entrepreneurship as a process of turning ideas into opportunities and opportunities into successful businesses through the practical application of one-to-one mentoring model, entrepreneurship awareness-building skills, personal empowerment skills, entrepreneurial/enterprise skills, business planning skills, business management skills, support services availing skills and business improvement skills. Though the risk of failure is always present, he takes risks by assuming responsibility for his actions. Learning from past experiences will help channel his actions to obtain better results and persistent efforts will yield success for sure.

S.S.Khanka (2009) in his book Entrepreneurship Development illustrates the personal characteristics of successful entrepreneurs as hard work, desire for high achievement, high optimism, independence, foresight, good organizing capacity, and innovativeness. According to the author, the success of a small enterprise is, to a great extent, attributed to the success of the entrepreneur himself.

R. Nagendran, Dr. K. Banumathy and Dr. N.R.V.Prabhu (2002) in their book Entrepreneurship Management and Development of Small Business xxv explain the characteristics of successful entrepreneurs. A successful entrepreneur is always aware of the new developments and change that take place around him in the society and is prepared to adapt to the changing needs of the society. He is the pivot around which all another factor of production, productive resources, and techniques should revolve. He combines talents, abilities and drives to transform the resources into profitable undertakings.

B. Badhai (2001) in his book Entrepreneurship for Engineers defines the entrepreneur as a person who has already started an enterprise or who is in the process of starting one. The author enlists the characteristics of an entrepreneur in Indian conditions as – need for achievement, risk-taking attitude, need to influence others, ability to sense opportunities, positive self-concept, level of expectation, initiative, inclination to accept challenges, independent thought and xxvi action, problem solving attitude, inclination for searching environment, time boundless, sense of dissatisfaction, result orientation, influence to get through bureaucratic red-tapism, financial soundness etc.

H. Nandan (2007) in his book Fundamentals of Entrepreneurship highlights on the ultimate success of any entrepreneurial endeavor. According to him, the success depends on the personality, that is to say, the composite characteristics, of the entrepreneur. The entrepreneurial personality denotes the xxx totality of the entrepreneur's character traits, including attitude, habits, emotional tendencies and behavioral patterns. Extraordinary personal traits not only constitute entrepreneurs but also serve to identify them from others.

Research Methodology

The research methodology of this paper is only descriptive. Data and information have been collected with the help of Books, Magazines, Newspapers, Research Articles, Research Journals, E-Journals, etc.

Objectives of the Paper

- To know about the features and characteristics of the business.
- To identify seven C's of business.

Features of Business

Exchange of Goods and Services: All business activities are directly or indirectly concerned with the exchange of goods or services for money or money's worth.

Deals in Numerous Transactions: In business, the exchange of goods and services is a regular feature and deals in some transactions.

Profit is the Main Objective: The business is carried on with the intention of earning a profit and it is the reward for the owner for running the business

Business Skills for Economic Success: A businessman needs experience and skill to run a business. He needs to possess good business qualities and skills.

Risks and Uncertainties: Business is subject to risks and uncertainties. There are also uncertainties that must be borne by the businessman.

Buyer and Seller: Business is a contract or an agreement between buyer and seller and every business transaction has minimum of two parties that are a buyer and a seller.

Connected with Production: Business activity may be connected with the production of goods or rendering of services.

To Satisfy Human Wants: Business is carried out to produce and supply of goods and services to promote consumer's satisfaction

Social Obligations: Modern business is service oriented and businessmen are conscious of their corporate social responsibility.

7 C's for Business Success

Clarity: Every businessman must be clear on who are they and what they want. The greater clarity on values, vision, mission, purpose and goals--the greater the probability of success in business.

Competence: A businessman should be competent to run the business. He must make excellent performance to achieve the primary goal and quality work to offer quality products and services.

Constraints: Every business has a constraint or limiting factor. The ability to identify the most important factor that determines the speed to achieve the business goals is essential to the success.

Creativity: The essence of a successful business is innovation. This is the ability to find faster, better, cheaper, easier ways to produce and deliver the products and services.

Concentration: The ability to concentrate single-mindedly on the most important thing and stay at it until it is complete is an essential prerequisite for success. No success is possible without the ability to practice sustained concentration on a single goal or task, in a single direction.

Courage: First of all every businessman needs the courage to begin, to move out of their comfort zone in the direction of the goals and dreams, apart

Continuous Action: The entrepreneur is always trying new things and, if they don't work, trying something else. It turns out that most entrepreneurs achieve their success in an area completely different from what they had initially expected. But because they continually reacted and responded constructively to change, trying new methods, abandoning activities that didn't work, picking themselves up after every defeat and trying once more, they eventually won out.

Factors that Contribute to the Success of a Business

Sound business strategy tied to the organization's core competency. The strategy is interpreted into what gets done in the organization and the benefits are being realized.

Good Employees are empowered to do an amazing job and always finding better ways to do things. The employees are good at solving problems. They like to come to work and you aren't even bribing them with free stuff!

Leaders inspire, and they motivate. They know what they are doing and keep up with and handle change brilliantly. The business thrives in its industry. Leaders understand their market, stay on top of the industry trends and changes. They understand how to deal with the issues of the industry.

Healthy Corporate Culture. People collaborate, brainstorm, and share knowledge. People care about their work. Not too much politics. Performance metrics measure the right things – to ensure the organization achieves its goals. For the most part, people get along together well and they are positive, glass half full types.

The organization can handle constant change. The business has the structure in place to change strategy (and associated execution) when the major change occurs in the market. The organization is flexible and adaptable. The organization is agile because it has processes, procedures and standards that are just right – not over done (too much rigidity and processes causing inefficiency) or under done (everyone just does whatever!).

The company is proactive, not reactive. Issues are anticipated. The risk is managed. The business is quickly solving problems and making the sound, rapid decisions as required to succeed.

The organization has creative thinkers and innovators. They are coming up with better ideas than the competition.

The organization has the information and data they need to make the best decisions at all levels of the company.

Conclusion

To realize the full potential and to achieve the business goals probable entrepreneurs must develop the virtues of integrity, courage and persistence. They have to practice the qualities of clarity, competence, creativity, concentration and continuous action as natural as breathing. They have to accept complete responsibility of their life and everything that happens to them, and especially for the way they think in every area.

The secret of a successful business is that, if you learn more things, try more things and persist longer, you will succeed greatly. If you launch toward your goal and resolve in advance to never give up, your success is virtually guaranteed.

Successful new business venture and economic development do not just happen they are the result of the combination of the right environment, planning, effort and innovation. The right combination of this can only be achieved by the efforts to be taken by entrepreneurs.

References

- Ram Charan, Competing for Growth, Business Standard, Chennai, Volume IX, No.1, February 2011.
- Ranju Sarkar, Scripting the future, Business Standard, Chennai, Volume IX, No.1, February 2011.
- Rathore B.S. and Saini J.S., Entrepreneurship, Wheeler Publishing, New Delhi, 2001.
- Saini J.S. and Rathore B.S., Entrepreneurship, Wheeler Publishing, New Delhi, 2001.
- Shirsat B.G., Charge of the entrepreneurs, Business Standard, Volume IX, No.1, February 2011.
- Surinder Kapur, Raghavendra Rao and Sanjeev Bikhchandani, Genesis Creating value through the entrepreneurial initiative, Vikalpa, April-June 2007. ccxxxiv
- Tripathi, D., Occupational Mobility and Industrial Entrepreneurship in India - Historical Analysis, Developing Economies, March 1981, pp. 52- 68.
- Verma, M.C., Entrepreneurs Attitudes towards Organizing and Risk-taking, Indian Psychological Review, 1978, pp. 213-29.

Web Sources

- <http://bizconnect.standardbank.co.za/start/introduction-to-entrepreneurship/7-essential-principles-for-business-success.aspx>
- <http://invisibleluck.blogspot.com/2013/02/business.html>
- <http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/120181/2/thesis.pdf>
- <http://snaptube-apk.com/why-not-learn-more-about-businesses.html>
- <http://snaptube-apk.com/why-not-learn-more-about-businesses.html>
- <http://www.destinywomen.co.ke/business101-paddy-mwangi/>
- <http://www.programmaster.org/PM/PM.nsf/U pcomingSymposia/AED27D50237FAE2C8525829E005FFE39>
- <https://ibrahimsameer.files.wordpress.com/2012/11/unit-1-introduction-to-business.pdf>
- <https://www.bayt.com/en/specialties/q/132906/what-are-the-factors-that-may-lead-to-the-company-s-aimed-motives/>
- <https://www.coursehero.com/file/20616909/SUCCESSFUL-ENTREPRENEURS/>
- <https://www.entrepreneur.com/article/173484>
- <https://www.entrepreneur.com/article/173484>
- <https://www.majortests.com/essay/International-Business-Global-Chocolate-Wars-Between-Mars-P3RAVGGQSS.html>
- <https://www.studymode.com/essays/Corporation-And-Business-59264775.html>